

Dynamic Multi-Band and Multi-Fiber Packet-Optical Networks with Wavelength and Waveband switching

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Abstract: *This paper presents a packet-optical network architecture that incorporates waveband switching alongside traditional wavelength switching. The performance evaluation highlights the trade-offs between blocking probability, the number and size of wavebands, and the number of fibers.*

Keywords: *Switching systems, architectures, and network integrations, Photonic switching systems and networks*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the coming decade, the society, industry and economy are anticipated to undergo a significant digital transformation, driven by advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Sixth Generation of mobile networks (6G), which will enhance quality of life and drive progress across various sectors. However, these advancements present significant challenges for packet-optical transport networks in terms of capacity demands. Assuming a conservative 25% Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), consistent with modest traffic forecasts, the projected spectrum demand by 2031 is expected to reach 50 THz [1].

Traditionally, packet-optical networks are designed with a multi-layer architecture, where IP routers are interconnected through an optical wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) network, known as IP over WDM. The packet layer follows a hierarchical architecture, where traffic is aggregated from access routers to core routers (e.g., from 10GE/25GE lower-capacity ports to 400GE/800GE higher-capacity ports), optimizing port and link utilization. The optical layer is implemented using reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADMs), interconnected by optical fiber pairs (one per direction). Optical channels routed through multiple ROADMs enable to dynamically establish virtual IP links between routers, forming a partially meshed virtual network topology (VNT). Since each intermediate IP router introduces latency and consumes critical resources—such as switch fabric capacity, optical interface ports, and power—network operators aim to minimize unnecessary IP hops to reduce costs. A cost-effective strategy is to eliminate intermediate routers that serve primarily as transit nodes by provisioning direct virtual IP links between routers at different hierarchy levels. The rationale is that once IP traffic has been efficiently aggregated to fill a given port capacity at a given hierarchy level, additional transit router hops offer little to no aggregation benefit.

In order to address capacity demands, multi-band WDM systems are an emerging solution to significantly enhance optical network capacity by utilizing the full optical spectrum across all available bands in single-mode fibers (SMFs). A straightforward approach is to deploy band multiplexers/demultiplexers to manage each band individually while performing wavelength switching for each one. While this method delivers optimal performance, it introduces substantial complexity—and consequently, higher costs—at ROADMs, as the wavelength switching stage must be replicated for each optical band. This complexity is further increased when deploying multiple fibers per link to achieve even greater capacity. The FLEX-SCALE project addresses this challenge by introducing a Multi-Granular Optical Node (MG-ON) architecture, which incorporates waveband division multiplexing (WBDM) switching alongside traditional WDM switching, providing a more scalable and efficient solution [2]. This approach enables to introduce VNT at the wavelength layer, where ROADMs are no longer connected by SMFs but by virtual WDM links [3][4]. This paper presents the proposed architecture and dynamic routing and resource assignment algorithm for multi-band and multi-fiber packet-optical networks combining wavelength and waveband switching. We evaluate the performance considering WDM-only and WDM/WBDM switching, showing the trade-off between blocking probability, the number and size of wavebands, and the number fibers.

II. MULTI-BAND AND MULTI-FIBER PACKET-OPTICAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

The FLEX-SCALE MG-ON architecture is built around a novel switching subsystem called the WaveBand-Selective Switch (WBSS). The WBSS is implemented as a compact, programmable, and rapidly reconfigurable photonic integrated circuit (PIC) capable of dynamically processing the entire ultra-wide WDM optical spectrum. It can flexibly partition the spectrum into continuous, flat spectral bands (referred to as wavebands) as needed and switch them to multiple output ports. Fig.1. illustrates the target multi-band and multi-fiber packet-optical network architecture. The underlying waveband layer consists of WaveBand Cross-Connect (WBXC) nodes, interconnected by multiple optical fibers in a partially meshed topology. Each WBXC performs waveband switching between its ports, routing wavebands across the physical network. This layer establishes end-to-end waveband channels (WBCh), spanning multiple WBXCs between a pair of source-destination WBXC client ports (i.e., the add/drop ports of the waveband layer).

Fig.1. a) Multi-band & Fiber optical network architecture b) Multi-granular optical node architecture c) Routing and Resource Assignment Algorithm

Each WBXC integrates three ROADMs, one per optical band (e.g., S, C, L), connected at the WBXC client ports. These ROADMs handle wavelength switching, either between WBXC client ports or as add/drop operations to the ROADM client ports. The wavelength layer enables end-to-end optical channels between source-destination ROADM client ports. A WDM transponder array connects to the ROADM client ports. These transponders can be fully tunable across all bands (S, C, and L) or specific to a single band (S, C, or L). Finally, IP routers with grey client transceivers are connected one-to-one with the transponder array, completing the end-to-end connectivity.

The key advantage of the IP over multi-granular (WDM/WBDM) optical network architecture is that ROADMs in the wavelength layer are no longer physically connected by optical fibers but instead by virtual WDM links, generating a VNT as in the IP layer. When a waveband channel is provisioned between a pair of WBXC client ports in the waveband layer, it effectively creates a virtual WDM link in the wavelength layer between a pair of ROADMs. This approach enables a transition from a static ring/mesh topology, where optical channels must traverse multiple transit ROADM hops, to a dynamically reconfigurable VNT, eliminating intermediate transit ROADMs that act primarily as pass-through (transit) nodes. The rationale is that once multiple optical channels have been efficiently routed along the same path between a source and destination ROADM, there is little to no benefit in individually routing them through wavelength-level switching at intermediate ROADMs. Instead, waveband switching can be applied, significantly reducing complexity. By adopting this strategy, the efficiency of the WDM layer is enhanced, minimizing hardware and operational costs—following a similar optimization approach as in the IP layer.

Fig.1. b illustrates the internal architecture of the MG-ON. The design includes a D-degree WBXC with F optical fibers per direction. Each optical fiber terminates in a $1 \times M$ WBSS, resulting in a total of $F \times D \times 2$ WBSS units. The WBSS units are interconnected using the same route-and-select architecture employed in ROADMs. Consequently, each WBSS connected to an input fiber must be interconnected with all WBSS units connected to output fibers, except those in the same direction. This configuration requires $F \times (D-1)$ pass-through ports per WBSS. Additionally, each WBSS includes one dedicated port per supported optical band (e.g., three ports for the S, C, and L bands) for add/drop functionality (WBXC client ports). At the wavelength layer, there is one ROADM per supported optical band (three ROADMs in Fig. 1(b)). Each WBXC client port terminates in a $1 \times N$ Wavelength-Selective Switch (WSS), leading to a total of $F \times D \times 2$ WSS units. The number of pass-through ports required for interconnecting the WSS units within a ROADM is $F \times (D-1)$, while the remaining ports are allocated for add/drop operations (ROADM add/drop ports). We assume that each add/drop port supports only one wavelength at a time. If multi-band transponders are available, a single add/drop stage can integrate all add/drop ports from the three ROADMs. Otherwise, if only single-band transponders are available, separate add/drop stages per node must be deployed. The transponders are connected to the add/drop stage(s) via the ROADM client ports.

The algorithm for routing and resource assignment is illustrated in Fig.1. c. The physical layer corresponds to the waveband layer, denoted as G^b —each node pair is connected by multiple fiber links F having wavebands. G^w represents the graphs at the wavelength layer, which is virtual. In this we have a lightpath request LR from source s to destination d with C number of parallel connections, each connection requires SS^c slots. The routing procedure begins at the wavelength layer. The first step is to check if a route with contiguous and continuous slots is available from s to d on G^w . If a valid route is found, set the C optical channels from s to d . If no valid route is found at this layer, the process proceeds to the underlying waveband layer—the task is to find a route with a continuously available waveband. If such a route is found, reserve the waveband end-to-end, assign the corresponding WBCh, and add an edge from s to d on G^w . Once the waveband has been provisioned, rerun the algorithm to find a path through the newly established virtual link and set the optical channels for parallel connections C . If no suitable waveband route is found, the request is blocked.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We simulate a Spanish Telefónica optical backbone network consisting of 65 nodes and 135 bi-directional links, with an average nodal degree of 3.5 [4]. Each link operates in the S, C, and L bands, offering a total bandwidth of 19.2 THz. Each slot bandwidth is 200 GHz (with 12.5 GHz granularity), a total of 96 slots are available per fiber link. The nodes are divided into 11 core nodes and 54 service nodes. A non-uniform traffic model is used, with 66% of the traffic between core-service nodes, and 34% between core-core nodes. Service nodes establish connections with their nearest core node(s). Connection requests follow a Poisson distribution, with a mean holding time of one unit. The simulations consist of 5 iterations, each processing 100,000 requests. The offered load (in Erlangs) for all the test cases is measured at for 1% blocking probability (95% Confidence Interval).

Fig. 2. Offered load versus the number of parallel connections for 800 Gbps, considering Fiber = 1, 2, 4, and 8. The load values are measured for WDM (baseline) and three WDM/WBDM configurations.

Fig. 2 illustrates the offered load for various MG-ON technologies, against varying number of parallel connections while considering multiple fibers. These plots correspond to scenarios where each connection requests 1 slot (200GHz). A WDM-only switching network is the baseline, while WDM/WBDM is evaluated under different waveband distributions. We consider three WDM/WBDM configurations: 3 wavebands (32 slots per waveband), 6 wavebands (16 slots per waveband), and 12 wavebands (8 slots per waveband). As the number of wavebands increases, the performance of WDM/WBDM improves. For instance, when using 1 fiber and 3 wavebands for 8 parallel connections, the performance of WDM/WBDM drops by approximately 77% compared to WDM. However, increasing the number of wavebands from 3 to 6 reduces this performance drop to 38.5%, demonstrating the benefit of finer waveband granularity. When the number of wavebands is large enough that each request (comprising multiple connections) occupies an entire waveband, connections bypass the WDM layer and the performance of WDM/WBDM matches that of WDM. Additionally, adding a greater number of fibers further improves the performance of WDM/WBDM. With 8 fiber and 3 wavebands for 8 parallel connections, the performance drop reduces to 15.41%. Similar trends are observed for the higher number of parallel connection requests.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The results demonstrate that increasing the number of wavebands and fibers significantly improves the performance of WDM/WBDM networks, reducing the performance gap with WDM and highlighting the benefits of finer waveband granularity and greater fiber availability.

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